

Development of a low-cost solar desalination device using porous silica for efficient freshwater production

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ABSTRACT

Water scarcity limits access to fresh water despite 71% of the Earth's surface being covered by water, with 96.5% in seawater form. Conventional desalination methods, like reverse osmosis, are costly and energy-intensive. This project develops a low-cost desalination system using evaporation and condensation, incorporating hydrophilic porous silica synthesized from sodium silicate. The porous structure facilitates seawater transport, while insulation reduces energy loss, accelerating evaporation. To enhance efficiency, carbon black is integrated into the silica, improving solar absorption. Silica with 23.1% carbon achieved an evaporation rate of $2.08 \text{ L}\cdot\text{hr}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$, surpassing the natural evaporation of $1.21 \text{ L}\cdot\text{hr}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$, while preventing microbial and dust contamination.

KEYWORDS: Porous Silica; Solar Desalination; Seawater; Fresh Water; Solar Energy

1. INTRODUCTION

The growing global population has increased the demand for clean drinking water, leading to a critical issue: water scarcity. Climate change, rising temperatures, and melting polar ice caps further exacerbate this problem by impacting natural water sources. According to the United Nations, 2.3 billion people are currently living in water-stressed areas, and by 2025, this number could rise to 4 billion if current trends continue.¹ Despite 71% of the Earth's surface being covered by water, 96.5% is seawater, leaving only 3.5% as fresh water—most of which is inaccessible for direct consumption.² To address this, solar desalination has emerged as a sustainable and eco-friendly solution to convert seawater into potable water through a simple and energy-efficient process.

Solar desalination is a process that uses solar energy to separate salt and other impurities from seawater, producing drinkable water. It provides a clean, renewable, and sustainable alternative to conventional desalination methods, which are often complex and costly. By harnessing solar power, desalination becomes more cost-effective and accessible, addressing global water scarcity.³ Research on carbonized natural green flora for solar desalination has explored biodegradable materials such as mushrooms, bamboo, carrots, and corn. These materials undergo carbonization to form blocks that enhance sunlight absorption, improving water evaporation efficiency. This method achieves over 99% salt reduction, with a maximum water yield of 12.32 liters per square meter per day.^{4,5}

Seawater evaporation processes typically occur slowly due to the large surface area and volume of water, as heat must penetrate deep into the water. Traditional systems focus on evaporating thin surface layers exposed to heat. Although conventional solar evaporation can produce clean water, it

still contains bacteria and microorganisms, posing health risks. Moreover, typical systems generate only about 7 liters of clean water per square meter per day, which is insufficient for human needs.⁶ This research seeks to increase water production to 20-30 liters per square meter daily, suitable for household and community use, while improving water quality with efficient filtration materials to reduce filtration time. These factors are crucial for advancing solar desalination technologies to meet the diverse needs of communities.

The design of a novel evaporator focused on key factors such as cleanliness, salt removal, and the elimination of impurities, including bacteria. The invention in this study was designed to filter seawater more efficiently by using foam to allow the system to float and increase porosity, enhancing evaporation. Plastic was used to seal and compact the system for collecting clean water (Figure 1). Materials were selected for their ability to filter substances effectively without introducing contaminants. Porous silica was identified as an ideal material due to its high pore volume, mesoporous structure of 2–50 nm pore size, large surface area, and resistance to heat and chemicals.⁷⁻⁹ Additionally, its hydrophilic nature enables water transport via capillary action, enhancing the desalination process.¹⁰ The hydrophilic porous silica transports water from the seawater surface to the top layer, while its carbon content, which gives it a black color, allows it to absorb light more efficiently, speeding up the evaporation process.¹¹ This facilitates the efficient removal of salt from seawater during the solar desalination process.

The objectives of this research are as follows:

- 1) Develop porous silica materials for efficient solar desalination systems to enhance seawater permeation on thin substrates.
- 2) Develop porous silica material for efficient solar desalination systems to optimize seawater evaporation on foam surfaces.
- 3) Determine the optimal thickness of foam sheets for desalination devices.
- 4) Design and construct a device for producing fresh water from seawater using the solar desalination process.

Hypotheses of the experiment are as follows:

- 1) The amount of water evaporated from the device is greater than the amount naturally evaporated over the same period.
- 2) The device is capable of producing water that is clean and safe and meets the established standards for drinking water quality.

Figure 1 The core of the solar desalination device is a floating foam with silica-filled holes for seawater percolation. The foam's surface is coated with silica to enhance evaporation. This study focused on the synthesis and testing of porous silica with varying silica-to-carbon ratios to optimize performance.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Synthesis of porous silica

Prepared a 10% w/w solution of Sodium Silicate and a 10% w/w solution of $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.¹² Added carbon powder to the CaCl_2 solution in quantities of 0, 5, 10, 20, and 30 grams per 100 grams of $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Transferred the CaCl_2 solution into a blender and added the sodium silicate solution at a 1:1 ratio. Filtered the precipitate formed and washed it with water through a filter. Dried the precipitate at 100 degrees Celsius and ground it into a powder.

2.2 Study of the percolation efficiency of sodium chloride solution using silica with different carbon proportions

This experiment examined how different proportions of activated carbon in silica affect the percolation time of a 3.5% w/v NaCl solution (dyed with red food coloring) through transparent rubber tubes. The experiment was conducted in a controlled environment within a laboratory setting. Controlled variables included tube size and length, solution volume, and concentration. The procedure involved cutting 5 cm rubber tubes, marking 1 cm increments, inserting porous silica with varying carbon proportions, and positioning the tubes in beakers with a gap for solution permeation. Observations were recorded, and each trial was repeated three times for accuracy.

2.3 Study of the evaporation efficiency of sodium chloride solution

A 4.5 cm diameter foam (1 inch thick) was perforated with 0.5 cm holes using a laser cutter, with nylon attached to the bottom for support. Porous silica, optimized for solution penetration, was placed into the holes, with additional synthesized silica (with varying carbon content) layered 2 mm above the foam. The foam samples, with and without silica, were placed in the 100-mL beakers containing 50 mL of 3.5% w/v NaCl solution (synthetic seawater). The surrounding environmental conditions during the experiment were regulated by enclosing the setup within a custom-built light box, which had a 150-watt halogen lamp positioned 15 cm away, applied heat for 2 hours, with beaker weights and silica surface temperatures recorded every 30 minutes. The proportion of carbons mixed in silica was varied as the independent variable, while the amount of water evaporated from the sodium chloride solution served as the dependent variable. Controlled variables included the cross-sectional size and thickness of the foam, the volume and concentration of the sodium chloride solution, the intensity and duration of heat application, and the weight of silica used in each sample.

The experiment was repeated three times for accuracy. To investigate the effect of foam thickness, the similar experimental protocol was performed using a 4.5 cm diameter foam with thicknesses of 0.5, 1, and 1.5 inches. The thickness of the foam served as the independent variable, while the quantity of water evaporated from the sodium chloride solution acted as the dependent variable. Controlled variables included the cross-sectional size of the foam, the proportion of carbon mixed in silica, the volume and concentration of the sodium chloride solution, the intensity and duration of heat application, and the weight of silica used in each case.

2.4 Study of the diameter of the wetted circle during heating

This experiment investigated how heating affects the diameter of the wetted circle on foam. The surrounding environmental conditions were regulated in a custom-built light box, which had a 150-watt halogen lamp positioned 15 cm away, the same light box used in Section 2.3 of the experiment. The diameter of the wetted circle served as the dependent variable, while the distance between the light bulb and the cross-sectional size of the foam, the intensity of the light used for testing, the duration of heating, and the thickness of the foam acted as control variables. The wetted circle is the area that is permeated by NaCl solution all the time. Foam of the optimal thickness (from previous experiments) was perforated with three 0.5 cm holes, spaced 4 cm apart. The best-performing porous

silica was placed inside the holes and applied to the foam surface. The foam was floated on the 3.5% w/v NaCl solution-filled tray and exposed to a light source at the distance of 15 cm for 1 hour. The wetted circle diameter was then measured.

2.5 Study of the Reusability Efficiency of Silica

The surrounding environmental conditions were regulated in a custom-built light box, which has a 150-watt halogen lamp positioned 15 cm away, the same light box used in Sections 2.3 and 2.4 of the experiment. The independent variable in this experiment was the number of usage cycles, while the dependent variable was the amount of water evaporated from the seawater. Controlled variables included the size, thickness, and proportion of carbon mixed in the silica foam, as well as the volume of the seawater, the intensity of light used in the test, the duration of heat application, and the weight of silica used in each case. Foam (4.5 cm thick) was prepared by drilling 0.5 cm holes into a 1-inch-thick sheet using a laser cutter, with nylon attached to the bottom using adhesive. The foam holes were filled with porous silica optimized for seawater percolation, while the surface was coated with silica optimized for evaporation. The foam samples were placed in the beakers containing 50 mL seawater, weighed, and heated for 2 hours. Weight loss was recorded, and the experiment was repeated for multiple cycles.

2.6 Solar desalination device

The experiment was performed to investigate the effect of different solar desalination device designs on various water quality parameters. The experimental environment was an open outdoor area with consistent and unobstructed sunlight exposure at the same location for all trials. Testing began at 1:00 p.m. and was conducted over 3 hours. The characteristics of the device served as the independent variable, while turbidity, pH value of obtained fresh water, and salinity acted as dependent variables. Controlled variables included the testing location, temperature, testing duration, and surface area of the foam cut. The floating desalination foam was scaled up to a 40 cm diameter, using optimized silica filling and coating for seawater percolation and evaporation. Three models, each with distinct features (Figure 2), were tested to assess their impact on water quality.

Model 1: Grooves were carved along the foam's edge to house a transparent acrylic dome for water collection. Rubber tubing connected to the grooves, with silicone securing the tubing. The dome was placed over the foam, and the tubing was connected to a water reservoir. Condensation formed in the dome and flew into the rubber tube to the water reservoir.

Model 2: The dome was connected to a PVC pipe, leading to water collection. Condensation formed in the PVC pipe and flew into the water reservoir.

Model 3: A clear acrylic ring was attached to the foam, and a transparent rubber tube was connected to the acrylic ring. The water channel was integrated into the dome, unlike Model 1 where the channel was attached to the foam.

The devices were floated in a container of seawater collected from Cha-am Port, Thailand. The seawater sample had a salinity of 31.9 ppt and a turbidity of 25.9 NTU. After three hours of sunlight exposure starting at 1:00 p.m., water samples were collected for analysis of salinity, turbidity, and pH.

Model 1

Model 2

Model 3

Figure 2 Design and construction of solar desalination device - Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Percolation efficiency of NaCl solution through silica with varying carbon proportions

It was found that silica with 16.7% carbon by mass allowed NaCl solution to permeate faster than silica with 0%, 4.8%, or 9.1% carbon (Table 1). This was due to the combination of capillary action and the smaller pores of carbon, which are classified as microporous (smaller than silica's mesoporous range of 2–50 nm). The higher proportion of carbon increases microporosity, enabling capillary forces to pull the sodium chloride solution a greater distance, thus enhancing permeability compared to lower carbon proportions.¹³ However, the rate of permeation decreased when the carbon percentage exceeded 16.7%. This might be due to increased hydrophobicity with a higher percentage of carbon.

Table 1 Relationship between time and distance that NaCl solution can permeate through modified silica

No	Mass of carbon per 100 g of silica	Percentage of carbon in silica (%w/w)	Time that substance takes to move in different distances (minutes)				
			1 cm	2 cm	3 cm	4 cm	5 cm
1	0	0	1.1 ± 0.1	3.4 ± 0.1	7.2 ± 0.5	13.4 ± 1.2	24 ± 5
2	5	4.8	0.5 ± 0.1	3.0 ± 1.1	6.6 ± 1.2	13.3 ± 0.6	24 ± 4
3	10	9.1	0.4 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.2	3.6 ± 0.1	7.6 ± 0.4	14 ± 2
4	20	16.7	0.25 ± 0.04	1.2 ± 0.2	2.5 ± 0.4	5.5 ± 1.4	10 ± 3
5	30	23.1	0.26 ± 0.04	1.1 ± 0.1	3.0 ± 0.3	6.4 ± 1.1	11 ± 3

Table 2 Water evaporation facilitated by foam containing modified silica

No	Floating foam	Evaporation volume (mL)				Evaporation rate (L·hr ⁻¹ ·m ⁻²)
		30 mins	60 mins	90 mins	120 mins	
1	no foam	0.4 ± 0.2	1.2 ± 0.4	2.4 ± 0.4	3.8 ± 0.4	1.21 ± 0.24
2	no silica	0.08 ± 0.01	0.2 ± 0.02	0.3 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.1	0.16 ± 0.06
3	0% carbon (unmodified silica)	0.7 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.1	2.65 ± 0.03	3.8 ± 0.1	1.19 ± 0.08
4	4.8% carbon	1.1 ± 0.1	2.6 ± 0.6	3.9 ± 0.5	5.3 ± 0.7	1.69 ± 0.34
5	9.1% carbon	1.2 ± 0.1	2.6 ± 0.2	4.1 ± 0.4	5.5 ± 0.5	1.75 ± 0.23
6	16.7% carbon	1.1 ± 0.1	2.1 ± 0.3	3.9 ± 0.3	5.2 ± 0.4	1.67 ± 0.23
7	23.1% carbon	1.4 ± 0.2	3.2 ± 0.3	4.9 ± 0.4	6.6 ± 0.5	2.08 ± 0.30

Table 3 Water evaporation facilitated by foam of various thickness

No	Foam thickness (inch)	Evaporation volume (mL)				Evaporation rate (L·hr ⁻¹ ·m ⁻²)
		30 mins	60 mins	90 mins	120 mins	
1	0.5	1.0 ± 0.1	2.4 ± 0.1	3.7 ± 0.4	5.3 ± 0.4	1.7 ± 0.2
2	1.0	1.2 ± 0.2	2.9 ± 0.4	4.5 ± 0.5	6.3 ± 0.5	2.0 ± 0.3
3	1.5	1.2 ± 0.1	2.9 ± 0.1	4.4 ± 0.1	6.1 ± 0.1	1.9 ± 0.1

3.2 Evaporation efficiency of water on surfaces coated with silica of varying carbon proportions

A study on the effect of carbon proportion in silica on the evaporation of a 3.5% w/v NaCl solution was conducted using a circular surface (4.5 cm diameter) over three trials. Natural evaporation yielded 3.8 mL in 2 hours, while a floating foam without silica reduced evaporation to 0.5 mL in 2 hours. However, foam containing silica increased evaporation significantly (Table 2). Analyzing mass loss over time, the evaporation rate increased with carbon content. Foam coated with silica containing 23.1% carbon showed evaporation volume of 6.6 mL over two hours, corresponding to the evaporation rate 3.3 mL·hr⁻¹ and 2.08 L·hr⁻¹·m⁻², which was more effective than the natural evaporation rate of 1,205 mL·hr⁻¹·m⁻² from the water surface. This was because the black carbon-enhanced silica absorbed more heat than white silica, making it more effective. Therefore, incorporating 23.1% carbon silica on foam surfaces could maximize seawater evaporation in the solar desalination process.

A study on foam thickness and its effect on the evaporation rate found that the 1-inch foam gave the highest rate of evaporation (Table 3). The 0.5-inch foam exhibited the lowest evaporation rate due to poor heat insulation, allowing most heat energy to pass through rather than accumulating on the surface. In contrast, the 1.5-inch foam reduced evaporation efficiency as the sodium chloride solution took longer to reach the surface. The 1-inch foam provided the optimal balance between heat insulation

and solution transport, making it the most suitable thickness for maximizing evaporation efficiency in the invention.

3.3 Study of the diameter of the wetted circle during heating

An experiment was conducted to study the permeation and evaporation area when floating foam was heated. A floating foam sheet with 5 mm diameter holes filled with modified silica resulted in a wetted circle on the surface, with an average diameter of 2.92 ± 0.18 cm. This wetted circle represents the area continuously permeated by the NaCl solution, corresponding to the evaporation zone. Measuring the wetted circle helped optimize the spacing of water-conducting holes in the foam. If the holes were spaced too far apart, some areas would remain dry all the time due to slower solution permeation compared to the evaporation rate. Thus, spacing the silica-filled holes at 2.92 cm optimizes evaporation efficiency while minimizing silica waste.

3.4 The reusability of foam with modified silica

As the number of repeated uses increased, the evaporation efficiency of water decreased (Table 4). The reason was likely because of deposition on salt and other impurities on the foam surface, which reduced the efficiency of water penetration. This problem can be solved by washing the silica with water so that the salt will dissolve in the water and the silica can be reused.

Table 4 The relation between water evaporation volume and repeated use

Round	Water evaporation volume (mL)	SD
1	1.81	0.08
2	1.76	0.07
3	1.69	0.06
4	1.59	0.02
5	1.52	0.03

3.5 Quality of water obtained from the solar desalination process

The quality of the water obtained from each model was compared against the standard values set by the Department of Health.¹⁴ Model 2, which featured a PVC pipe connected to the top and a rubber hose covered with heat insulation, was unable to produce fresh water. This was due to the small size of the PVC pipe, which prevented water vapor from moving effectively inside, leading to excessive water vapor clinging to the dome-shaped surface. Analysis of water quality from Model 1 revealed that the turbidity of the fresh water did not meet the drinking water quality criteria. This was attributed to silica contamination in the gutter area on the foam surface, likely from the fabrication process. In contrast, when the water collection tube from the foam to the acrylic lid in Model 3, the condensed water met all the criteria for turbidity, salinity, and pH (Table 5).

Table 5 The quality of water obtained from evaporator model 1-3

Model	Turbidity (NTU) Standard value ≤ 5	Salinity (ppt) Standard value ≤ 0.25	pH Standard value 6.5-8.5	Pass
1	13.2	0.8	7.78	X
3	2.9	0.0	6.69	Pass

4. CONCLUSIONS

Silica with 16.7% Carbon had the fastest percolation rate, making it the chosen material to fill in the water-conducting pore with a diameter of 0.5 cm. Silica with a higher percentage of carbon

resulted in higher surface temperature, so silica with 23.1% carbon was chosen to coat the surface area of the foam to assist water evaporation. The foam thickness chosen for the product was 1 inch. The goal was to create a device capable of producing fresh water for drinking and domestic use from seawater with high evaporation efficiency without requiring energy, low cost, and could be further developed in the future. However, this device has some limitations, as it is only effective when used on land near the sea. Additionally, the current prototype is small; however, it can be made larger or connected to other units, which could improve its overall capacity. Its water output may also be unstable under real-world climate conditions such as storms or low sunlight. Despite these challenges, the innovation shows promising potential. With further development and scaling, it could offer a sustainable and practical solution to fresh water scarcity, especially in resource-limited regions and coastal communities.

5. AUTHOR INFORMATION

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Author Contributions

P.S., S.W. and K.P. conducted the experiments and design concept of the invention, data analysis, create an invention, research about scientific information, and drafting of the manuscript. U.J. and S.Y. served as project advisors.

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7. REFERENCES

- 1 UN Water. (2021). Summary Progress Update 2021: SDG 6 — water and sanitation for all. *UN Water*. <https://www.unwater.org/publications/summary-progress-update-2021-sdg-6-water-and-sanitation-all>
- 2 United States Geological Survey. (2019). *How much water is there on Earth?* U.S. Geological Survey. <https://www.usgs.gov/special-topics/water-science-school/science/how-much-water-there-earth>
- 3 Tao, P., Ni, G., Song, C., Shang, W., Wu, J., Zhu, J., Chen, G., & Deng, T. (2018). Solar-driven interfacial evaporation. *Nature Energy*, 3(12), 1031–1041. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-018-0260-7>
- 4 Greenlee, L. F., Lawler, D. F., Freeman, B. D., Marrot, B., & Moulin, P. (2009). Reverse osmosis desalination: Water sources, technology, and today's challenges. *Water Research*, 43(9), 2317-2348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2009.03.010>
- 5 Arunkumar, T., Lim, H. W., Denkenberger, D., & Lee, S. J. (2022). A review on carbonized natural green flora for solar desalination. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 158, 112121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112121>

- 6 Li, Z., Wang, C., Lei, T., Ma, H., Su, J., Ling, S., & Wang, W. (2019). Arched bamboo charcoal as interfacial solar steam generation integrative device with enhanced water purification capacity. *Advanced Sustainable Systems*, 3(4). <https://doi.org/10.1002/adsu.201800144>
- 7 Hanrahan, J. P., O'Mahony, T. F., Tobin, J. M., & Hogan, J. J. (n.d.). Mesoporous silica and their applications. *Sigma-Aldrich*. https://www.sigmaaldrich.com/TH/en/technical-documents/technical-article/environmental-testing-and-industrial-hygiene/waste-water-and-process-water-testing/mesoporoussilica?srsId=AfmBOopDLn48ePXVwoi0i6kvaouU5k2zOHZ5H7yGhs_MqXg_ke_bNUs6
- 8 Ariga, K., Vinu, A., Yamauchi, Y., Ji, Q., & Hill, J. P. (2012). Nanoarchitectonics for mesoporous materials. *Bulletin of the Chemical Society of Japan*, 85(1), 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.1246/bcsj.20110162>
- 9 Butt, H., & Kappl, M. (2009). Normal capillary forces. *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science*, 146(1–2), 48–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cis.2008.10.002>
- 10 Liu, J., Liu, J., Shi, F., Ma, C., Li, T., Chen, C., Wasim, M., Zhu, K., Sun, H., & Tian, Z. (2022). A facile pore size controlling strategy to construct rigid/flexible silica aerogels for super heat insulation and VOCs adsorption. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 450, 138196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.138196>
- 11 Paminto, J., Fianti, I., & Yulianti. (2021). The effect of surface color on the absorption of solar radiation. *Physics Communication*, 5(1), 27–32
- 12 Yodyingyong, S. (2017). *A method for producing a micron-size spherical silica aerogel* (PCT application No. WO2018124979A2)
- 13 Fukumori, Y., Nomura, T., Adschiri, T., Ohara, S., Saito, F., Naito, M., Okuyama, K., Kawahara, M., Suzuki, H., Sasaki, T., Fuji, M., Inagaki, S., Takeuchi, H., & Ando, Y. (2018). Structural control of nanoparticles. In *Elsevier eBooks* (pp. 49–107). <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-444-64110-6.00002-0>
- 14 Department of Health. (2020). Criteria for Recommendation of Drinking Water Quality Surveillance, B.E. 2563. *Bureau of Food and Water Sanitation Department of Health*. <https://foodsafety.anamai.moph.go.th/th/water-quality/204437>